

Enriching open metadata for preprints with Europe PMC

Mariia Levchenko¹, Melissa Harrison¹

¹EMBL-EBI, Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, Cambridgeshire

Open metadata challenges for preprints

Open metadata plays a pivotal role in the scholarly ecosystem, enabling transparency, reproducibility, and democratization of knowledge. It allows researchers and institutions to track, analyze, and understand the processes behind scientific discovery. It supports bibliometric and meta research studies to identify patterns, biases, and inefficiencies within the science system. It boosts interoperability between diverse systems and platforms, facilitates seamless integrations and enables development of new tools and value-add services.

Despite its undisputable value, a significant portion of research information remains locked within closed proprietary infrastructures. In recent years, there have been a number of important developments to make scholarly metadata openly available. This includes the Initiative for Open Citations, Initiative for Open Abstracts, Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, just to name a few. This reflects the growing understanding of the open metadata importance within the scholarly community.

Even where metadata is open, it may not be easily accessible. For organizations seeking to leverage open metadata, availability often hinges on how the data is presented and delivered. Simply being “open” is not enough if the metadata is fragmented, inconsistent, or stored in formats that are difficult to interpret. Building new tools and services that integrate or enhance open metadata requires programmatic access to structured, machine-readable data that adheres to standardized formats and protocols. Such access enables automation, scalability, and interoperability, which are critical for developing innovative solutions that can handle the vast and growing volume of scholarly information. Without these capabilities, the potential of open metadata to transform research and innovation remains unrealized.

This is particularly true when it comes to preprints. Preprints are early-stage research outputs that are openly shared before formal peer review. They enable rapid research communication, are typically free for authors and readers, and provide an opportunity for early feedback. Preprints hold a promise of transforming research communication by enabling experiments with innovative forms of publishing and peer review. Understanding the effectiveness and impact of these new approaches will require meta research studies that rely on rich and accessible metadata. However, despite their significance, preprints can be difficult to analyse. They are typically scattered across many servers and platforms, with limited free programmatic access and bulk download options. Due to resource constraints and limited adoption of community standards, preprint servers differ in the metadata they create and surface. While many servers deposit preprint metadata with DOI registration agencies, such as Crossref, DataCite, or Japan Link Center, completeness of registered metadata varies across providers. Metadata gaps can also happen due to a lack of community standards, with divergent practices on registering preprint versions, withdrawals or review status.

Facilitating preprint discovery and reuse

Recognising the need for a centralised source of preprints and existing challenges around their discovery and reuse, Europe PMC set out to become a hub for preprints in the life sciences. Europe PMC is an open, community-driven infrastructure that provides access to a large corpus of biomedical preprints. It is a life science literature database, developed by the European Bioinformatics Institute and supported by a group of 35 international science funders as their repository of choice. Europe PMC is a part of the PubMed Central (PMC) International archive network and provides access to millions of abstracts and full text records from a range of sources.

Europe PMC covers nearly 900,000 preprints from 34 preprint platforms, with new trusted sources added regularly. Servers are screened based on a set of guidelines, to ensure that indexed content conforms to accepted scientific standards. Beyond high-quality metadata, Europe PMC offers a corpus of 70,000 full text preprints in a structured machine readable format. This includes COVID-19 preprints, as well as preprints supported by Europe PMC funders. To support preprint analyses, Europe PMC provides free and open programmatic access and bulk download options.

Europe PMC started indexing preprints in 2018, initially covering 9 platforms that registered Crossref DOIs for their preprints. To ensure transparency and improve discoverability, we introduced a set of requirements for what we considered essential metadata. This includes a persistent identifier, title, abstract, posted date, and author names. However, several preprint providers at the time did not include these in their Crossref submission. It became apparent that before we could expand preprint coverage we needed to work closely with the preprint community to help develop common metadata practices and improve metadata provision. Europe PMC was also uniquely placed to address some of the metadata gaps by leveraging its infrastructure as well as its expertise in text analysis. Here we describe our efforts to enrich preprints with open metadata to create a more connected ecosystem for preprint discovery and analysis.

Enriching open metadata for preprints

To create a comprehensive preprint record, Europe PMC integrates diverse metadata sources, employs text-mining and machine-learning techniques to extract information from full text, and engages in efforts to drive adoption for best practices around metadata creation and capture. Preprints in Europe PMC are enriched with citation and funding information, community reviews, associated data and more.

Europe PMC places a great importance on the use of persistent identifiers. For example, author information for preprints is enhanced with ORCID iDs, retrieved programmatically from ORCID itself. Europe PMC also provides a linking tool to allow authors to connect preprints in Europe PMC to their ORCID records. We add Research Organization Registry identifiers (ROR IDs) to affiliations for full text preprints in Europe PMC, which provides open persistent identifiers for research organisations, helping to disambiguate institutional names and connect them to relevant research outputs.

Europe PMC integrates preprints into the scholarly infrastructure assisting their inclusion into research workflows, such as article citation, funding reporting, and credit and attribution. We monitor preprint citations to help evaluate preprint impact and examine its context within the

broader research landscape. Citation information in Europe PMC is determined from the reference lists of full text publications and preprints, and enriched with open citations available through Crossref metadata supplied by publishers.

Information about organisations that supported preprinted research is vital for transparency and accountability. Several research funders support or encourage inclusion of preprints in grant applications and award decisions, and many authors include a funding statement in their posted preprints. Europe PMC retrieves funding information for preprints via the Crossref API, where available. This is further supplemented by extracting grant award mentions for Europe PMC funders from the Acknowledgements and Funding sections of full text preprints.

Unlike journal articles, preprints are not static in their nature and can often be revised, reviewed, published, withdrawn, or removed. To track these preprint updates, Europe PMC has developed several mechanisms and offers the Article Status Monitor to view and export changes to the record. Preprint status in Europe PMC is clearly labeled on the preprint page and can also be tracked programmatically, with a dedicated module of the Articles API..

Some preprints are withdrawn or removed due to incorrect data, authorship or legal disputes, or erroneous posting. Currently, such a status change is not reflected in Crossref. Several preprint servers use the preprint title to indicate that a preprint has been withdrawn or removed. Europe PMC detects changes in the title and updates the publication type to “preprint-withdrawal” or “preprint-removal” accordingly, with nearly 2500 preprints suppressed from the scientific record.

As some preprints are submitted to journals and undergo journal peer review it is important to connect them with their corresponding published versions. To link preprints with journal articles Europe PMC combines information from two sources. Some links are provided by journal publishers or preprint servers using the Crossref relationship schema. In other cases, Europe PMC uses an automated process to match preprints and journal articles based on titles and first author surnames. Together, these approaches allowed us to identify over 330,000 published preprints in Europe PMC, to date.

While the process of posting preprints is decoupled from journal-organised peer review, there is a growing number of preprint review initiatives that provide preprint feedback. Europe PMC collates review information from 20 platforms and communities available through aggregation platforms, such as Society and Early Evidence Base, as well as preprint evaluations registered with Crossref. Over 15,000 reviewed preprints can be found in Europe PMC.

To foster connections between preprints and data, Europe PMC identifies data citations using a text-mining pipeline. Data DOIs and data accessions for nearly 50 biological resources are extracted from preprint abstracts and full text, supporting the FAIR data principles and enabling data discovery.

Summary

Europe PMC exemplifies how open infrastructure can bridge gaps in the preprint ecosystem. It provides valuable support for metascience research, supporting evidence-based approaches to improving research practices.